

FEATURES OF THE LEXICAL LAYER OF DIALECTAL UNITS IN THE EXPLANATORY DICTIONARY OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

Bobosherova Madina

named after Sharof Rashidov

Student of Samarkand State University

Telefon: +998935038650

bobosherovamadina@gmail.com

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Abstract

The Uzbek language has a centuries-old history. As a result of the economic, political and social relations of our people with other nations, words from other languages entered. Persian-Tajik and Arabic words make up the majority of the acquired layer of dialectal words in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language. In this article, we will discuss the acquired dialectisms in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language.

Key words: dialect, dialectal units, acquired layer, dialectism, dialect household terms.

The fact that dictionaries occupy an important place in the spirituality and national culture of a certain people is a situation that does not require proof. They reflect the knowledge gained by the society in a certain period. Dictionaries use certain social devices to obtain information, inform the reader about a specific event or situation, introduce him to words in his own and foreign languages, provide the language, its vocabulary, and to regulate. with his help, he has a great burden, and it is necessary to constantly improve his form in keeping with the times. re-dictionaries, even if they are not modern perfect, lag behind the times to a certain extent, and the words record new relations between the things and events they represent, which came as a result of one or another change.

The new five-volume "Annotated Dictionary of the Uzbek Language" takes into account the new positive achievements of Uzbek and world lexicography, the innovations that happened in the lexicon of the Uzbek language during the years of Uzbekistan's independence. is a newly created dictionary

This explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language aims to collect and describe not only the entire vocabulary of the Uzbek language, but the vocabulary of the Uzbek language in wide use in a broad chronological framework

The norm of the dictionary is that it recommends the norms of spelling, pronunciation, word formation and its use of the literary language. For this purpose, the words are included in the dictionary according to their relationship to the national literary language, their place in it, and the scope of use. In the dictionary, the acceptable spelling of each word, its origin-etymology, in necessary cases, its pronunciation is indicated, its meaning (or meanings) is determined and explained, the words are defined meanings and their correct use in these meanings are proved by examples-quotes taken from Uzbek artistic and scientific literature and the press.

Among the words related to dialect: 1) words such as karavot-suri-charpoya, which are used in parallel in the literary language; 2) words such as gurun, manglai, konoq, which are

used in most dialects and are also found in written sources, even if they do not belong to the literary language; 3) words such as yelvizak, yelvagay, archimoq, arna, which do not have a variant in the literary language and are used in one or more dialects, are included

The dictionary of Uzbek folk dialects is extremely numerous and diverse, some of them have been studied phonetically and grammatically. But there are dialects that are still poorly studied lexically.

The following words were added to the dictionary of Uzbek folk dialects:

1. Words that are not found in the literary language, only characteristic of the dialect: büväk (Fergana, Andijan) baby.

2. Words that exist in the literary language but have different meanings in the dialects: kältak (Andijan, Fergana) kalamcha, chivin (Bukhara) pashsha, "muka".

3. Words that exist in literary languages and dialects, and in one of them have changed according to their meaning and gained stylistic significance: gor (Tashkent), ignorant (about a person).

4. Doublet words that have not yet been normalized in the literary language, that is, the dominant is not defined, and are used in parallel in fiction: tänčä (Tashkent) //sändäl (Fergana, Andijan) a place to sit and warm in winter, "sandal".

5. Words that have undergone a strong phonetic change and changed their original form

Only the most important words found in modern Uzbek dialects have been included in the dictionary. In order for the meaning of the words in the dictionary to be better understood by the reader, they were given in context, through illustrative examples taken from dialects. Although dialect materials were the main source for the dictionary, folklore materials were also used instead.

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In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the total number of lexemes given by dialect names is more than 900. Some of the words related to the dialect form their own layer, and some of them form the assimilated layer.

Lexical composition of Uzbek dialects.

Uzbek dialects, as a local form of the Uzbek language, combine most of its layers, therefore, the Uzbek language lexical layers are as follows:

1. Common Turkish words.
2. Similar words:
 - words borrowed from the Arabic language;
 - words borrowed from Persian languages;
 - Russian language and words acquired through it.
3. Words created under the conditions of the Uzbek language.
4. Special words of dialects.

Common Turkic words are used in most Turkic languages and dialects, and in Uzbek dialects they may retain their literary pronunciation or undergo a strong or weak phonetic change. This includes words such as yer/djer, ish/is, bash/bas, and various other fields. Common Turkic words make up a significant part of the vocabulary of dialects.

Words borrowed from the Arabic, Persian-Tajik Russian language are used in dialects, mostly phonetically simplified. The results of scientific research show that there are more

Persian-Tajik words in the vocabulary of dialects, fewer Arabic words, and very few Russian-international words, which means that such a word shows that it is due to the fact that the alignment process takes more time.

Based on this, we will consider the appropriate words included in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language below.

The past generations of the current Uzbek people lived in close contact with the Iranian (especially Tajik) speaking population. As a result of the economic and cultural relations between these two peoples, many Tajik words have become firmly established in the vocabulary of the Uzbek language. For example, lamp, zardov, charim, sinch, pipe, khakandoz, barkash, obdasta, curtain, match, carpet, sheet, footer, socks, paitava, poshna, lining, necklace, zarbob, top board, brick, khari, fence . The adopted Tajik words express concepts related to everyday life, household, gardening, farming, and crafts.

The fact that the Uzbek people have lived together with their brother Tajik people for a long time, and their mutual relations have also found expression in their languages. That is why many Tajik words can be found in the Uzbek literary language and its dialects. Most of these borrowed words are nouns, adjectives, adverbs and auxiliary words: ogoh // ada. -orf. alert, dāš//ada.-ord. dasht, dārāx//ad. Orf. a tree

Tajik words:

Doxt-Body deformity, shape, stature [5. 678].

Dogāv- Milk-yogurt serum.

Käläpätrā-Disorganized; He used to do his work in a chaotic, haphazard manner.

Källäpoš-Headwear

Kälānpā -A man with big feet.

Kät-Wide wooden bed [5. 331].

lāgān-A deep earthen vessel larger than a bowl

lättā-Silk fabric.

lungi-Towel, pinamak, a towel by the way.

nagmāgār-Sozanda, musician.

āftābpārāst- Sunflower.

pälākmürdā-The dried layer of polyz crops. p.

Pärdevār -A thin wall made of a row of bricks.

Pājāndāz -Blanket

Pāsirā-Estate.

Arabic words entered the ancient Turkic language from the 11th-13th centuries. This is due to the conquest of Central Asia by the Arabs during this period, they introduced their own alphabet to the local population, conducted state and official affairs in Arabic. Due to such reasons, a number of Arabic words have been absorbed into the Uzbek language. This process was limited by the decline of the Arabic caliphate during the reign of the Samanids (10th-10th centuries) and served as a religious language. In the current Uzbek language, the following words can be seen: article, philosopher, science, practice, poor, school, madrasa, literature, profession, book, pen, etc.

In Uzbek literary language, nouns, adjectives, adverbs, auxiliary words and verbs make up most of the words that came from Arabic, and in dialects, the main place is occupied by nouns. It should also be said that the number of Arabic words with j-locus is greater in urban

dialects than in rural dialects: aqil//ad.-orf. testament, kudrät//ad.orf. power, shärm//ada.-orf. like shärm.

Arabic words:

Rähbä -Open wide area, field.

Säjis-In general, horse.

sāqa-A stable for horses.

Tävr-Like, like; in a way

Talqin~tälqin-A song, a song.

Šätir- A special seat on which a khan or a king is seated and raised; distance, distance.

[5.596].

oqil-A person who becomes a guarantor or representative during marriage; representative

Qäläm-Tongue, tongue.

In short, the Uzbek language contains a number of words related to dialect in the explanatory dictionary. Among the words related to the dialect in the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the assimilated layer is the majority. Because no language in the world has enough resources to become rich. The explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language includes dialectal units that are understandable to most members of the society, and we reviewed some of the acquired words.

Foydalanilgan adabiyotlar:

1. Ashirboyev S. O'zbek dialektologiyasi. - T.: 2016. -B. 7-10.
2. Ишаев А. Ўзбек диалектал лексикологияси.-Т. :1990.-Б. 101-102.
3. Мадалиев А. янги луғат яратиш давр тақозоси //Ўзбек тили ва адабиёти. 2006. Н:4. -Б. 16.
4. Решетов В.В., Шоабдурахмонов Ш. Ўзбек диалектологияси. -Т.: 1978.- Б. 168-169.
5. O'zbek tilining izohli lug'ati 1,2,3,4,5-jildlar. -Т.:1971.
6. O'zbek xalq shevalar lug'ati. -Т.: 1971. -Б. 4.